

Structural and optoelectronic properties of Sb₂S₂O based photodetectors

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Abstract

Antimony-based 2D materials are one of the leading post-graphene materials, as they are promising for various applications due to their customizable properties and versatile synthesis methods, allowing an exceptional degree of control in developing 2D devices. We have investigated Sb₂S₂O-based photodetectors, demonstrating photoresponsivity in the UV-VIS spectrum. We have inspected material and device structural and chemical properties, which we correlate with obtained device performances. The reported best device responsivity is relatively high at 1.7 A/W, with a relatively low response time in a few hundred ms range, indicating photogating dominated nature, confirmed with performed power dependence of photoresponsivity. Additionally, we have demonstrated the ambient stability of Sb₂S₂O, showing that it can function without needing protective top coatings. This opens up possibilities for surface functionalization and further optimization of the device. We also observed a distinct anisotropy in its Raman spectra, most prominent for the mid-frequency peak corresponding to Sb-O stretching modes and the peaks from interlayer interactions, expanding the potential applications of Sb₂S₂O in polarization-sensitive electronic devices.

Keywords: Sb₂S₂O, Kermesite, Antimony, Two-dimensional devices, Photodetectors

1. Introduction

Our world consists of a vast number of minerals and crystals that have historically been exploited for many applications, from primary material utilization as different

tools to modern-day electronic components. Since the discovery of graphene, the first two-dimensional (2D) material, many reports have shown that with the reduction of three-dimensional bulk crystals close to two dimensions by reducing their thickness, materials exhibit unique

combinations of different properties, often drastically different from their three-dimensional counterparts.[1–4] Among many potential applications, 2D materials offer the most impact for optoelectronic applications, specifically photodetectors due to their bandgap tunability by layer dependence, heterostructure stacking or surface functionalization.[5,6] Furthermore, they often display high charge carrier mobility, nearly perfect switching performance, strong gate voltage controllability, and immunity to the short-channel effect.[7] For example, the presence of Dirac cones in monolayer graphene (G) means that its absorption is independent of the wavelength of incident light and is determined solely by the fine structure constant, resulting in a absorption rate of about 2.3%.[8] On the other hand, many transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) exhibit van Hove singularities in their band structures, facilitating strong light-matter interactions.[9] However, in their abundance so far, only a few thousand of 2D materials have been experimentally utilized, with many new ones yet to be investigated.[10]

Antimony-based materials are one of the attractive options for many applications among different potential 2D materials. Starting with two-dimensional antimony, antimonene, which stands out as one of the most promising post-graphene 2D materials discovered so far due to its structure, properties, and applications being highly customizable through both top-down and bottom-up approaches, allowing an exceptional degree of control in the development of 2D materials.[11,12] Furthermore, antimony oxides (e.g. Sb_2O_3) and sulfides (e.g. Sb_2S_3) thin films are used as microwave devices, switching devices, nanostructured electrodes, gas sensing industries and various optoelectronic devices.[13–15] On the other hand, research on $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ (Kermesite) has so far been limited to bulk structural and optical properties, with only a few papers investigating its properties in two-dimensional or thin layer forms. $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ is one of the secondary minerals found in Antimony mines, offering numerous natural sources, but there have also been reports on its chemical synthesis.[16,17] Furthermore, a few papers that investigated thin film $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ showed a bandgap up to 3 eV, indicating its suitability for various optoelectronic applications.[18–20]

In this work, we have investigated the structural and chemical properties of bulk $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ and devices based on exfoliated $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flakes. We have measured the optoelectronic properties of fabricated devices, whose performance we compared to theoretically obtained values and correlated their difference to induced materials contaminations and defects. Measuring the device's photoresponse under different illumination wavelengths, we showed that non-encapsulated flakes could be utilized for almost the whole ultraviolet-visible (UV-VIS) range photodetection in ambient conditions, with best-obtained photoresponsivity of 1.7 A/W and response time less than 500 ms. This offers potential for its surface functionalization for

further applications and device optimization. Furthermore, we showed an evident anisotropy signature in its Raman spectra, broadening the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ application potential for polarization-sensitive electronic devices.

2. Experimental methods

$\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ also known as mineral Kermesite originate from its classic locality in Pezinok (Kolarsky vrch deposit), Slovakia.

2.1 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out on a Phoibos 100 (Specs, Germany) with monochromatic Al source ($K_{\alpha 1} = 1486.7$ eV). For the measurement, the samples was placed onto a Cu conductive tape. For survey spectra, an $E_{\text{pass}} = 50$ eV with a step of 1 eV was used while for high-resolution core-level spectra an $E_{\text{pass}} = 20$ eV with a step of 0.1 eV was used. Compensation using a floodgun was employed to achieve a C 1s position of 284.8 eV.

2.2 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out on a Bruker D8 Discover (Bruker) with Cu X-ray source ($\lambda = 0.15418$ nm, $U = 40$ kV, $I = 30$ mA). Diffractograms were collected in a range from 10° to 60° range with a step of 0.02° and step time of 0.5s. Phase identification was carried out in HighScore plus software.

2.3 Scanning electron microscope and Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) Tescan Lyra dual-beam microscope with a FEG electron source was used to investigate device morphology. Imaging was performed at 5 mm WD and 10 kV of accelerating voltage in analysis mode with a secondary electron (SE) detector. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was used for elemental composition and mapping using an 80 mm² SDD detector (Oxford Instruments) and AZtecEnergy software.

2.4 Transmission electron microscope

Transmission electron microscope (TEM) images were obtained using a Jeol 2200 FS EFTEM equipped with a ZrO/W Schottky emitter (Field Emission Gun, FEG) in TEM mode. The operating conditions included an acceleration voltage of 200 kV, with magnifications ranging from $10,000\times$ to $800,000\times$.

2.5 Optical spectroscopy

Raman and PL spectroscopy was conducted within an argon glovebox on a WITec alpha300 R Confocal Raman

Microscope equipped with an Ultra-High Throughput Spectrometer. (Ulm, Germany) utilizing a 532 nm laser. The microscope is mounted on an antivibration table to minimize the effects of external vibrations. The measurement was carried out at room temperature using a Zeiss EC Epiplan-Neofluar Dic 100x/0.9 objective and a laser power of less than 1 mW, according to the recommendations, to prevent damage to the sample. The reflectance spectra were observed using a same setup within a 400 to 900 nm wavelength range, employing a white-light LED. To ensure the sample analysis's accuracy, the PDMS's spectra on glass, on which the bulk crystals were subsequently placed, were measured separately. Background smoothing and baseline correction were calculated using a custom-written Python script and the same script was then used to fit the peaks on Gaussians.

2.6 Atomic force microscopy

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ devices were recorded with a Nanosurf FlexAFM in ambient conditions. Non-contact AC (tapping) mode was used for data acquisition with a setpoint of around ~55%. Budget sensors Tap 190 Al-G silicon tips with a nominal spring constant of 48 N/m, a tip radius of 7 nm and a resonant frequency of 190 kHz were used. Images were processed with Gwydion and WSxM software.[21,22]

2.7 Optoelectronic characterization

Transport measurements were carried out at room temperature in ambient with Keysight source/measure unit (B2902A). Photocurrent spectroscopy was performed by measuring photocurrent during illumination by light with different wavelengths.[23,24] Thorlabs fiber-coupled LEDs (280 nm - M280F5g, 375 nm - M375F3g, 405 nm - M405F3g, 430 nm - M430F1g, 470 nm - M470F4, 530 nm - M530F3, 625 nm - M625F2, 850 nm - M850F3) with LED controlling drivers (Thorlabs LEDD1B) and Slim Photodiode Power Sensor S130VC with power and energy meter PM100USB from Thorlabs were used. The illumination power density of $P_{\text{dens}} = 2 \text{ mW/cm}^2$ was maintained during the experiment.

2.8 Density Functional Theory Calculations

The properties of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ in the bulk triclinic phase were investigated using first principle calculations. The structural parameters for the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ with the space group of $P1$ are provided in Figure S3 (a). Based on the experimental composition, the model for $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ was constructed using VESTA software. Upon optimization of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ structure, the intrinsic properties and Raman spectra simulation were systematically calculated. For structural optimisation, OTFG normconserving pseudopotential was used to simulate the interaction between electron and ion cores in geometric

structure optimization and single point energy calculations.[25] In contrast, CA-PZ- Local density approximation (LDA) functional was used to describe the exchange-correlation function.[26,27] The cutoff energy was set as 900 eV and the K point was $3 \times 2 \times 1$. The convergence threshold is 1.0×10^{-5} is used and we have used the finite displacement method for calculating Raman calculations.

2.9 Finite Element Method Calculations

Au/ $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ /Si as a model photodetector device was initially considered for finite element method calculations with COMSOL Multiphysics.[36] The simulation methodology couples the semiconductor and electromagnetic wave interfaces, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the device's performance under illumination. In the semiconductor interface, the electronic properties and behavior of the constructed device is solved through Fermi-Dirac equations. The frequency domain analysis allows precise modeling of optical absorption and generation rates at specific wavelengths given from 365 nm to 600 nm. In particular, this method calculates the complex electric field distribution throughout the device. Furthermore, to enhance the accuracy of capturing electric field variations and carrier dynamics, a fine mesh was adopted for the entire device. The obtained simulation results are validated with the experimental data, and the developed model is optimized by adjusting parameters such as layer thickness of the material $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, which is given as 50 nm as shown in Figure S7 (a).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ structural and chemical properties

The devices investigated in this work were exfoliated from natural $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ crystals originating from a classic Kermesite locality in Pezinok, Slovakia. First, we investigated the composition and structure by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis as displayed in Figure 1 (a). We performed two measurements. The first measurement was carried out on bulk crystals while the other one was performed on powder sample. The bulk crystal measurements, displayed in the lower section of Figure 1 (a), showed highly preferential orientation with only several reflections visible. The reflections at higher angles are magnified in the inset of Figure 1 (a) for more clarity. The second measurement on the powder sample displayed much higher number of reflections, as can be seen in the upper part of Figure 1 (a). This measurement confirmed the single phase purity of the material, with some of the most prominent reflections highlighted in the figure.

Surface chemical analysis was conducted using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), with the results shown in Figures 1 (b) to 1 (d). The survey spectrum in Figure 1 (b) highlights the presence of Sb, S, and O, which constitute the

Figure 1. Structural and chemical properties of bulk $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$. (a) X-ray diffractogram of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ of crystal sample, with inset of results at higher angle, on lower part and powder sample obtained from the same crystal on upper part. (b) X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy survey spectrum of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$. (c) XPS high-resolution S 2p spectrum. (d) XPS high-resolution Sb 3d and O 1s spectrum.

$\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ material, along with adventitious carbon contamination. The high-resolution core-level spectrum of S 2p, displayed in Figure 1 (c), reveals a single doublet located at 161.5 eV and 162.8 eV, attributed to S $2p_{3/2}$ and S $2p_{1/2}$, respectively. Although experimental reports on the XPS characterization of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ are limited, these peak positions align well with previous studies on metal sulfides.[28] Figure 1 (d) presents the Sb 3d and O 1s regions, where a direct overlap is observed between the Sb $3d_{5/2}$ component at 529.4 eV and the O 1s component at 529.6 eV. To deconvolute this spectrum, a fixed intensity ratio of 1.5 between Sb $3d_{3/2}$ (538.7 eV) and Sb $3d_{5/2}$ was used, with the remaining area attributed to the O 1s peak. The noticeable difference in intensity between the Sb 3d and O 1s components is largely due to their significantly different relative sensitivity factors (RSF), with Sb 3d having an RSF of 27.74, and O 1s an RSF of 2.93. After the deconvolution of the Sb 3d + O 1s region, the final

elemental ratio obtained was $\text{Sb}_{2.00}\text{S}_{1.98}\text{O}_{0.81}$, which is close to the theoretical value.

Following, we have investigated the optical properties of bulk $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ by performing photoluminescence and reflectance spectroscopy. Photoluminescence spectra shown in Figure 2 (a) reveal a rather strong signal, which we fitted on two Gaussians with obtained centre values of 653 nm and 694 nm. These peaks are most likely interband transitions arising from excitonic, defect or phonon-assisted emissions as previously observed in other 2D materials.[29–32] PL corresponds to the distribution of the lowest exciton energy states, while the reflectance spectrum represents the distribution of all exciton states. Analysis of the normalized differential reflectance data reveals the presence of multiple distinguishable peaks, as shown in Figure 2 (b). An increase in reflectance is observed at the beginning of the spectrum. This behaviour can be rationalized by the decline in photoresponsivity from ultraviolet (UV) to longer

Figure 2. Optical properties of bulk $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ crystal used for further exfoliation and device fabrication. (a) Photoluminescence spectroscopy with fitted data on two Gaussian peaks. (b) Reflectance spectroscopy with fitted data on five Gaussian peaks.

wavelengths. The peaks at 437 nm, 458 nm and 512 nm are likely attributable to high-energy interband transitions between the conduction and valence bands or defects present within the material.[33] The peaks observed at 654 nm and 740 nm correspond to peaks observed in PL spectra. The peak at 654 nm exhibits negligible stoke shift, indicating that this peak corresponds to neutral exciton.[34–36] At the same time, the peak at 740 nm exhibits a redshift of almost over 100 meV, which indicates phonon-assisted emission.[29,31]

3.2. $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ devices morphology

$\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flakes were exfoliated using the standard Nitto tape method and, via polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamping, transferred on top of prefabricated Au electrodes on Si/SiO₂ wafer, as shown in Figure 3(a).[4,37,38] Devices were fabricated inside an argon glovebox equipped with motorized XYZ stages, with which we controlled the movement of PDMS with $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flakes and Si/Au substrate, as illustrated in Figure S1. Nitto tape was used for the initial exfoliation of the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ crystal, as illustrated in Figure S1 (a). Subsequently, exfoliated flakes were pressed several times against the tape to reduce flake thickness and finally, a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) stamp was used to pick up the thinnest flakes from the tape, as shown in Figure S1 (b).[39,40] In this work, PDMS sheets were bought from Gel Pack company and larger sheets were cut onto smaller arbitrary shapes compatible with the substrate on which the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ are transferred. At this step, the PDMS stamp has several flakes, from which, with the optical microscope, the best one is chosen for stamping, as illustrated in Figure S1 (c). Next, the PDMS stamp was attached to the first set of motorized XYZ manipulators and on the second set, the patterned Si wafer was placed. Figure S1 (d) shows the step during which PDMS with $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ is placed onto the patterned Si wafer. During the placing of the PDMS stamp, the step is

monitored by an optical microscope or camera and controlled with a set of micromanipulators with which one can precisely control the position and separation of PDMS and substrate. To ensure that $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ has higher adhesion with the substrate, PDMS is slowly separated in small steps with a z-axis manipulator while heating the substrate on 70°C, as shown in Figure S1 (e).[38] The front of the adhesion is monitored via an optical microscope to increase separation speed in the areas of no interest and reduce it in the areas where $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ is targeted for transfer. After the complete separation of PDMS, the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flake is left on top of Au electrodes patterned on Si/SiO₂ wafer, as shown in Figure S1 (f). Same method was utilized for exfoliation and transfer of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ on TEM grids, from which TEM images were acquired, as shown in Figure S2, where we confirm material uniformity and minimal defect sites within the same plane height.

Instantly after fabrication of the devices, we measured Raman spectroscopy to confirm that the exfoliated flakes are indeed $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ and not a different compound (such as Sb_2O_3 and Sb_2S_3) that can be found around natural antimony minerals. First, spectra were recorded inside the glovebox, and all showed the same features with negligible variation of peak position and width between all investigated devices. As shown in Figure 3 (b), the Raman spectra of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ show narrow peaks dominated by peaks at 48.65 cm⁻¹ and 317.82 cm⁻¹ with several peaks in between, per previous reports.[41] We performed polarised Raman spectroscopy, and as shown in Figure 3 (b), the most dominant peaks, marked with black arrows, have significantly smaller intensity with 90° polarisation (aligned perpendicular to the long-cleaved edge of the flake). In contrast, some peaks, such as those at 130.19 cm⁻¹ and 231.12 cm⁻¹, marked with green arrows, maintain the same intensity regardless of laser polarization. We performed DFT calculations of Raman freestanding 2D $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$, as described in experimental methods, with the most intense

peaks obtained at 33.98 cm^{-1} and 308.57 cm^{-1} , as shown in Figure S3 (b). The mid-frequency modes above 300 cm^{-1} correspond to Sb-O stretching modes, while the peaks below 50 cm^{-1} can arise from interlayer interactions. These interlayer interactions can include van der Waals forces or weak bonding between layers. In contrast to the calculated peak dominated by Sb-S stretching and bending modes, around 177.67 cm^{-1} , our experimental Raman spectrum appears suppressed or significantly shifted, which could arise from substrate interactions. We repeated Raman spectroscopy after ambient

exposure of devices for more than 90 days, and we noticed a slight drop in intensity, which can be attributed to the thin H_2O layer formed on the sample surface. However, most importantly, we did not observe any variation in comparison with spectra recorded after fabrication, showing that the

$\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ can be used for ambient operation devices without the need for protective coating layers. Notably, certain 2D materials, such as black phosphorus (BP), are highly reactive to oxidation effects that cause their rapid degradation.[42] Other 2D materials, like transition metal dichalcogenides

Figure 3. Morphological and structural analysis of $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ devices. (a) Optical micrograph of one of the fabricated devices. (b) Angle-dependant Raman spectroscopy of the device shown in (a) with polarisation-sensitive peaks by black arrows and nonsensitive with green arrows. (c) SEM image of a second investigated device with indicated transfer-induced contaminations and bulk $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flakes by pink and cyan arrows, respectively. (d) EDS spectrum of the device with corresponding elements for each peak. (e) AFM image of thinness investigated device with indicated PDMS residues by pink arrows. (f) Lineprofile taken from the white dashed line indicated on (e).

(TMDs), are generally stable under ambient conditions, but their optoelectronic properties are sensitive to air exposure.[43] This sensitivity arises from structural imperfections such as grain boundaries, edges, and surface vacancies.[44] When exposed to air, the material interacts with water, oxygen molecules, and other adsorbed species, leading to doping effects and altering its properties.[45,46]

After initial inspection via optical microscopy and Raman spectroscopy, we performed additional morphology analysis via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and chemical analysis by energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Figure 3 (c) shows an SEM image of one of the devices on which we performed EDS analysis, with transfer-induced wrinkles and bulk $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flakes indicated with green and cyan arrows, respectively. All devices showed the expected chemical composition of Sb ($L\alpha 1$) at 3.60 keV, S ($K\alpha 1$) at 2.46 keV and O ($K\alpha 1$) at 0.52 keV, as depicted in the typical EDS spectrum in Figure 3 (d). Additional peaks in the spectrum correspond to Si ($K\alpha 1$) at 1.74 keV and Au ($M\alpha 1$) at 2.12 keV that originate from patterned Au electrodes and Si wafer. Since we have worked with Si with a SiO_2 layer on top, we did not analyze exact ratio of each elements as it is impossible to differentiate oxygen contribution from substrate and flake itself. The distribution of elements over the surface is shown in Figure S4, clearly demonstrating that Sb and S elements are present on the flake area, Au in the position of electrodes, while Si and O cover the whole surface but are strongest in the clear part of the channel.

We investigated more than ten devices with thicknesses ranging from 35 nm to 100 nm, which we determined by atomic force microscopy (AFM). The thinnest device is shown in Figure 3 (e), on which transfer-induced contaminations, i.e. PDMS residue, are indicated by pink arrows. For optoelectronic characterization, we chose devices with a thickness of 50 nm because of minimal defects and contaminations, as we used standard device fabrication techniques without special optimizations to minimize transfer defects such as wrinkles and cracks. Cracks and wrinkles often occur as the PDMS can locally deform during transfer, which induces new cracks and enlargement of pre-existing ones.[47] PDMS-induced contaminations and local straining of flakes can be minimized in future with UV-ozone pre-cleaning of the PDMS surface before exfoliation and subsequent thermal annealing.[47] Figure 3 (f) shows the line profile taken from the white dashed line indicated in Figure 3 (e), from which the thickness of Au electrodes and $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ flakes are determined around 10 nm and 35 nm, respectively.

3.3. $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ devices photoresponse

Before investigating the photoresponse of the device, we measured the electrical properties of fabricated $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ devices in the ambient under the dark. As shown in Figure 3, devices were fabricated on Si/ SiO_2 wafer patterned with pairs

of Au electrodes with a channel length of 5 μm . Current-voltage (I-V) sweeps were done, with drain-source voltage V_{DS} sweeps from -20V to 20 V and constant gate voltage V_{G} (from - 25 V to 25 V). As seen in the output curve in Figure 4 (a), devices exhibited relatively strong Schottky behaviour, which we tried to minimize by utilizing graphene contacts with and without hBN encapsulation, as shown in Figure S5 (a) and (b), respectively, and by thermal annealing in a vacuum. However, we did not observe any significant improvement in device performance, so we focused on the devices with pure Au contacts that were not optimized with additional processes.[48,49] Ambient transfer characteristics of the field effect transistor (FET) were also analyzed, with a Si wafer used as a back gate, but as the devices required high electric fields (both V_{G} and V_{DS}) to start to react on them, we have reached the dielectric limit of SiO_2 and started to measure significant leakage current before we could reach saturation. For further research on electrical properties, we suggest utilizing other 2D metal contacts (e.g. doped WSe_2 or WS_2) and additional buffer layers that could lead to fermi-level depinning and enable top-gate configuration.[50] For example, hBN or LaOBr could be used as coating layers, leading to device parameter enhancement.[51]

Following the electrical test, we investigated the device's photoresponse with white light and LED lights with specified wavelengths. The photocurrent I_{ph} was determined by monitoring the current before, during, and after illumination with monochromatic light, while a 10 V potential was applied to the $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ via Au electrodes. Figure 4(b) shows the OFF-ON-OFF illumination period with white light, while Figure 4(c) shows illumination with specific wavelengths. After illuminating the sample, rapid current growth can be seen, with a slow saturation trend. The same trend is also present when illumination is turned off and the decay starts. Due to cyclic illumination and long saturation time, the decay from the previous illumination is still present seconds before the new illumination period, so I_{OFF} were aligned at zero for more straightforward navigation. Device response time can be derived from the 10%-90% method, i.e. as the time which passes from achieving 10% to 90% value of saturation photocurrent.[52,53] Additionally, by subtracting the current ($I_{\text{OFF}}=10\% I_{\text{saturation}}$) from the on current ($I_{\text{ON}}=90\% I_{\text{saturation}}$), the persistent photoconductivity (PPC) effect is eliminated from further photocurrent analysis.[54] Figure 4 (d) shows device responsivity at different illumination wavelengths, with $P_{\text{dens}} = 2 \text{ mW/cm}^2$. It is visible that the devices show photoresponse above 600 nm, with the device cut off most likely around 750 nm wavelengths, in line with the values obtained for bulk PL spectroscopy shown in Figure 2(d) and indicating that the optical bandgap is less than previously reported 3 eV.[18,19] This demonstrates that $\text{Sb}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}$ photodetectors show functionality in almost the whole UV – VIS spectrum range.

The relationship between photocurrent and illumination power follows the power law: $I_{PH} \propto P^\beta$ where the exponent β is a factor determining the background of the photoresponse. The absence of charge recombination and trapping processes leads to a linear relationship, while with the more prominent defect density and trap states, the β value reduces.[6,55,56] Figure 4 (e) shows measured photocurrent dependence on illumination power, which by fitting gives a $\beta=0.32$, which indicates the photogating nature of devices, with significant charge recombination and trapping processes. Photocurrent

generation is governed by two mechanisms: photoconductance and photogating.[56] In photoconductance-driven devices, photoexcited electrons and holes are separated by the applied bias voltage, leading to an increase in current. On the other hand, for photogating-dominated devices, photoexcited electrons drift under the influence of the bias voltage, while holes become trapped. This results in additional electrons entering the channel. For each drifting electron reaching the drain electrode, a new electron from the source enters the channel to maintain charge conservation.

Figure 4. Optoelectronic characterization of Sb₂S₂O devices. (a) I-V sweeps with different gate voltage applied. (b) White light photoresponse, with 30s OFF – 30 s ON – 30s OFF interval. (c) Photoresponse under LED light illumination with specific wavelengths. (d) Device photoresponse for different illumination wavelengths. (e) Power dependence of the photoresponse for 375 nm wavelength illumination. (f) Finite element simulation of device photoresponsivity for different illumination wavelengths.

Consequently, the photoconductive gain is proportional to the ratio of electron drift time to hole trapping time. [57] Devices governed by a photogating mechanism usually exhibit long response times and high responsivity.[24,58] Our device photoresponsivity, calculated as $R_{ph} = I_{ph}/P_{ch}$, the ratio of I_{ph} and illumination power over channel P_{ch} , falls in the middle to upper range of previous reports on other 2D photodetectors, with determined best photoresponsivity of $R_{ph}=1.7$ A/W.[59] Furthermore, best-obtained detectivity was $D^*=1.9*10^9$ Jones, calculated by following formula $D^* = (R_{ph}\sqrt{A})/(\sqrt{2eI_{dark}})$, where A is the area of the photosensitive channel, e the unit charge and I_{dark} dark current. This represents the middle range, which is expected for ambient operation of nonencapsulated 2D photodetector.[6,59] Noise equivalent power (NEP) equals the minimum optical power where the photocurrent can be distinguished from the noise current, we obtained value as low as $NEP \approx 10^{-14} W/\sqrt{Hz}$, calculated by $NEP = \sqrt{AB}/D^*$, where B is frequency bandwidth. Response time indicates the response speed of the photodetectors upon turning on or turning off the illumination; rise time is defined as the time from 10% to 90% of I_{ON} , while recovery as the time from 90% to 10% of I_{ON} . [5] As illustrated in Figure S6, our devices show a response rise time of $\tau_{rise} \approx 500$ ms and a recovery time of $\tau_{rec} \approx 700$ ms, comparable with previously reported values for photogating-dominated photodetectors based on other 2D materials.[24,58,60] For comparison, we performed finite element method calculations of Sb_2S_2O photodetectors, with the simulated electric field across the Sb_2S_2O device for incident light of different wavelengths, as described in the experimental section and depicted in Figure S7 (b-e) with the photoresponse results summarized in Figure 4 (f). Obtained results show that pure Sb_2S_2O photodetectors exhibit values of photoresponsivity up to 0.12 A/W, which is more than order of magnitude lower than our experimentally obtained values. This is most likely as simulations do not include various defect and trap states which play important role in photogating dominated photodetectors.[6,59]

4. Conclusion

We have demonstrated the functionality of Sb_2S_2O photodetectors in almost the whole UV-VIS spectrum by investigating devices' photoresponse under different illumination wavelengths. We have determined the photogating signature of the device's photoresponse via performed power-dependent measurements, with reported best device responsivity of 1.7 A/W and response time in a few hundred ms range. Moreover, we showed that Sb_2S_2O has ambient stability and that it can be utilized without any coating top layers, which offers potential for its surface functionalization for further applications and device optimization. Moreover, the observed PL and anisotropy signature in its Raman spectra broadens the Sb_2S_2O

application potential for polarization-sensitive electronic devices.

Associated content

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Supporting information including scheme of device fabrication, TEM and SEM/EDS data, Simulated Raman spectra, optical microscopy images of device, photoresponse measurement and simulated electric field within the device.

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Notes

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Data availability statement

The datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the study are accessible via the Zenodo repository: <https://zenodo.org/records/14558302>.

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